

WHY STUDENTS ARE CHOOSING CRIMINAL JUSTICE MAJORS

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Abstract

A survey was sent out in a mass email to all criminal justice-associated students to participate. A total of 207 participants answered a series of questions about why they chose their major/minor, whether they have had a past loved one within the criminal justice system, what they plan to do, and a few demographic questions. I hypothesized that the most chosen influence among criminal justice majors will be personal experiences and the least chosen will be salary. I also hypothesized that women will be more likely to choose personal experiences as their influence compared to men. My last hypothesis was that men will be more likely to choose the career path of police officer compared to women. Findings revealed that gender did have a significant impact on students' reasoning for choosing their major and a future career path. It also revealed that the greatest influence was "general interest" and the lowest was "other." These answers will help explain why students are choosing a criminal justice major and help further the research on why students are choosing criminal justice majors.

Introduction

My senior honors project is based on the question, “Why do people choose to go into the criminal justice field?” that was raised during the introductory conversation with my now mentor, Dr. Christine Gardiner. We were discussing how the field itself is very diverse in the motivation for entering; we ourselves had different reasons for choosing the major/career. I chose to study criminal justice with my psychology major to understand why criminals chose to commit such heinous crimes, while others chose the major to serve their community. Research has discovered multiple factors for choosing a criminal justice major, such as parent’s influence, their personal experiences, media, the danger of the criminal justice field, and more.

The Influence of Others

Family members, peers, mentors, counselors, professors, and more will most likely influence students decisions when choosing a career and therefore a major. While some students report media was a big influence for choosing their major, others mentioned counselors and their professors had set them up on the correct career path (Collica-Cox & Furst, 2019). Conversations with professionals may encourage students to discuss what they truly want out of a career and move forward with what they need.

While other studies found a slight difference in the input of others including high school counselors, friends or family members are not as influential as other factors. Instead, Kuehn, Ridener, and Scott (2019) found that a general interest in the study, future job promotions and opportunities, and relevance to the real world were the most important factors for choosing a criminal justice major. The researchers believed other influences such as parents or counselors were not as influential as the research the student does on their own for their own major.

The Influence of Media

The influence of media is seen to be a huge factor for students choosing criminal justice majors. The “CSI effect” is described to greatly affect their viewer’s opinion on the criminal justice system (Stringer & Murphy, 2020). Crime shows often depict a fast process where a crime is committed, detectives find clues and suspects, and the criminal is caught within one hour. The CSI effect continues to distort the perception of how society views the criminal justice system whether it’s how the court room works, forensic testing, defendant/prosecutor’s roles, or the detective’s role (Collica-Cox & Furst, 2019). The desirability to be able to catch the killer quickly with exciting twists and turns may attract potential students. Though some studies do not directly connect the desire of being in the criminal justice field with crime fighting shows, many do discuss the *excitement* and *thrill* is a significant factor when choosing their criminal justice major (Courtright & Mackey, 2004). Students believe the field itself is exciting, but where do they get this perception? From crime-fighting shows, news outlets, and other media. Other studies also demonstrated the influence of media but focused on news outlets concentrating on stories from police officers. It found criminal justice majors have had greater media exposure compared to other majors due to the relevance of real world issues (Choi, 2019). Though these students demonstrated wanting to work as a criminal justice professional, they “felt uncomfortable to recall negative images of the police when reporting their attitudes toward the police” (Choi, 2019). Although this can demonstrate that crime-fighting shows may have a positive influence on future criminal justice majors, it also bombarded them with negative images as well that they must consider.

Some researchers believe media is not as influential as other factors, instead they are choosing the major from general interest and they believe the major is closely related to the real

world. They found that only 23% of participants in their study chose crime-related shows for a major influence in choosing their criminal justice major (Stringer & Murphy, 2020). Though this percentage to be less than originally thought, they did find people who choose this major tend to watch more crime related shows and movies (Stringer & Murphy, 2020). The researchers believe the relationship was not a causation, but a correlation; meaning people did not watch crime shows then chose the major, but rather that people who like to watch crime shows also like to major in criminal justice.

The Influence of Previous Experience

I did not include specifically the factor of victimization in my current study but added the option of choosing “personal experiences” to include their own personal experiences as well experiences of others who were close to them. A study found 83% of study participants had an experience with someone close to them or themselves being a victim (Eren, Leyro, & Disha, 2019). This indicated many criminal justice majors who have experienced victimization may use their experience to decide the criminal justice system is unfair. This may motivate students to fight oppression or advocate for equality amongst those in the criminal justice system (Eren, Leyro, & Disha, 2019). Another study specifically focused on arrest impacting their students. They found that students who were arrested or saw people close to them arrested for racial injustice were motivated to advocate for justice in their community (Disha, Eren, & Leyro, 2020). Continuing in the path of becoming a criminal justice major they are forced to hear other traumatic stories of arrest or other victimization stories where it continues to influence them in the career path.

With the influence of being a victim or seeing victimization with others, surprisingly there are also studies that discover less empathy in criminal justice majors compared to other

majors. Courtright, Mackey, and Packard found a strong negative relationship between empathy and criminal justice major students (2005). In some cases, they were extraordinarily low, which is startling because many people would wish their law enforcement to have some kind of empathy. Other findings have confirmed this finding by discovering criminal justice students have more “salient attitudes of punitiveness” than other majors (Mackey & Courtright, 2000). Their attitudes of punitiveness continued to increase within their college career.

An interesting finding was found with experiences of arrest due to immigration status. “Second generation students who witness arrest are more motivated than 3rd generation or later counterparts to want a career which can help them to solve problems” (Disha, Eren, & Leyro, 2020). Second generation status may feel the pressure of following their parent’s and making decisions for themselves.

Other Influences

Other researchers found connections of choosing a major to the student’s personality traits. Hunter and Meshkati (2020) believed students were aware of their own characteristics and were able to connect it to a major that they found most appealing. For example, if students’ believed they were observant and empathetic, they might connect with a psychology major because psychologists are seen as being empathic and observant. Another study specifically looked at the contrast of the characteristics, conscientiousness, and neuroticism in criminal justice majors and non-criminal justice majors. Kuehn, Ridener, and Scott (2019) saw the correlation of criminal justice majors and the personality trait of conscientious, which included being organized, self-disciplined, and dependable. It is not known if these students were aware of their personal characteristics when choosing their major, but there is a strong positive correlation between being a criminal justice major and the personality trait of conscientious. There also have

been studies that discovered people showed interest in working in law enforcement in order to gain personal status and power (Walters & Kremser, 2016). Though these reasons may not be agreeable to the masses, personality traits such as these are relevant to some leaders in law enforcement now.

Another aspect that was focused on was the background knowledge they may have had in the past that influenced their choice of major. Internships or jobs would allow them to view a certain career from an inner perspective and may alter their perception of the career. In agreement, 27% of responses from this study believed internships was a major influence for the major they chose (Hunter & Meshkati, 2020). Some high school students have used their internship experiences to further their passion. This would allow them to turn away certain career paths while attracting to them others.

With the research discovered, I hypothesized that the majority of participants will choose “personal experience” as their greatest influence for becoming a criminal justice major. I also hypothesized the fewest students will choose “salary” for their greatest influence of becoming a criminal justice major. My third hypothesis is that women are more likely to choose “personal experiences” for their greatest influence compared to men. My last hypothesis is that men are more likely to choose the career path of becoming a police officer compared to women.

Methods

I sent out a survey to all 1581 criminal justice students at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) asking for their reasons for choosing their criminal justice major/minor. From the 1581 of students who were invited to participate in the survey, 229 of those students responded. Once the data were reviewed and cleaned, 207 of the responses were included in these results. The survey contained fourteen questions about their greatest influence for choosing

their criminal justice major/minor, their interest for their career path, as well as demographic questions. It was constructed in Qualtrics and timed to take two to three minutes to complete. After obtaining Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval, an email was sent during the first week of class by the administrator of the CSUF criminal justice department. This included every CSUF student who is registered as a CRJU major or minor, no one was excluded. Two additional reminder emails were sent at one-week intervals to improve the response rate. It is unknown whether every student who was sent an email received the email or opened the email.

Once the data were received, I input it into SPSS 28 that allowed me to organize, clean, and convert the data into the results we have now. The gender within this participation pool consisted of 117 females, 45 males, and five “other.” The five “other” include nonbinary, prefer not to say, and other gender. The age range was 18 to 47, with the average of 21 years. Participants described their ethnicity as: 12.2% White, 2.4% Black, 12.8% Asian, 65.9% Latinx, 4.3% Other Race (including multiple ethnicities), and lastly 2.4% preferred not to say. This was close to representative of the criminal justice department student population which are: 10% White, 2% Black, 10% Asian, 71% Latinx, and 3% Other. The CSUF criminal justice department does not have a representative for “prefer not to say.” In order to obtain better results, I made a composite of gender. The option “Other” includes “non-binary”, “other”, and “prefer not to say.” There was a total of one “other,” two “prefer not to say,” and two “non-binary.” I also decided to make a composite of influence and added the options “helping others.” Some answers were represented answer choices while multiple written answers described helping their community or society in general. There was a total of 14 written answers of helping their community or others. I also decided to make a composite of career in order find the best results. Specifically, I added the option “homeland security” because of the four written answers,

including homeland security or border control. The rest of the written answer were able to fit into one of the options or left for “other.”

Results

H₁ and H₂: Why Students Are Choosing to Study Criminal Justice

The first and second hypotheses included the influence for choosing their criminal justice major. Participants chose “general interest” at 56.8%, “personal experiences” at 18.9%, “generational” at 10.7%, “helping others” at 8.3%, “salary” at 3.6%, and “other” at 1.8%. The first hypothesis stated that the majority of students will choose “personal experiences” as their greatest influence for choosing a criminal justice major, this was not supported. The greatest influence that participants chose was “general interest” at 56.8%, while “personal experiences” was second at 18.9%. The second hypothesis stated the least chosen influence for becoming a criminal justice major will be salary, but this was also not supported. The least chosen influence was “other” at 1.8% with “salary” being a very close second at 3.6%.

H₃: Gender Differences in Motivation

The third hypothesis claimed women are more likely to choose “personal experiences” as their reason for choosing a criminal justice major compared to men. This was supported with 13.6% of women and 4.1% of men choosing personal experiences as their greatest influence. The chi-square found for this hypothesis is $X^2(10,169) = 22.6, p < .001$, finding a significant difference in choosing an influence for their criminal justice major between gender.

H₄: Gender Difference in Career Interest

The fourth hypothesis proposed men will be more likely to choose the career path of becoming a police officer compared to women. This hypothesis was supported with 9.5% of men choosing the career path of becoming a police officer and 4.7% of women choosing this career

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path. The chi-square for this hypothesis is $X^2(22,169) = 56.76, p < .001$, finding a significant difference in men choosing the career path of becoming a police officer compared to women.

Discussion

H₁ and H₂: Why Students Are Choosing to Study Criminal Justice

The first hypothesis suggested the majority of students will choose “personal experience” for their biggest influence, but this was not supported. The majority of students chose “general interest.” Some of the responses of those participants choosing general interest answered they began to take an interest from television crime shows and high school or career experience. The CSI effect may be the reasoning for students describing television crime shows for choosing a criminal justice major (Collica-Cox & Furst, 2019). Many of the participants specifically recalled *Criminal Minds*, *Mind Hunter*, *CSI*, and understanding the CSI effect has affected themselves. Though the majority of criminal justice students chose “general interest” for their greatest influence, “personal experiences” was a close second. Some of the responses from these participants included family members in the criminal justice system and the victimization of family members or themselves. Though “personal experiences” was not highly chosen, those who did choose this as greatest influence did discuss their victimization experiences as mentioned in past research.

The second hypothesis proposed the least chosen influence will be “salary,” but this was not supported. The least chosen influence was “other.” Some of the responses for other included, being an easy career path and always wanting a career in the legal field. I originally thought salary would be a low influence because the criminal justice field is generally a selfless career

path. I also believe if students were after a high salary career, they would have chosen a major that is more correlated with high salaries such as business, computer tech, or biotech. Though it was not the lowest chosen influence, it was a very close second (and lowest among the choices provided) demonstrating how criminal justice is generally not linked to high salary careers.

H₃: Gender Differences in Motivation

The third hypothesis suggested women will be most likely to choose “personal experience” compared to men and this was supported. The significant findings demonstrated gender was an important factor whether the participant chose “personal experiences.” Some of the responses from the women choosing “personal experiences,” included family domestic violence, victims of sexual assault in family, family members in prison system, and poor encounters with law enforcement. I believe women have more victimization experiences than men, therefore would choose personal experiences as choosing their major.

H₄: Gender Difference in Career Interest

The last hypothesis believed men will be more likely to choose the career path of becoming a “police officer” compared to women, this was supported. The significant findings demonstrated gender was an important factor whether the participant chose the career path of becoming a “police officer.” In general, there has been a high population of men in the police force compared to women; only about 12% of officers in the general police force are women (Gardiner & Hickman, 2017). While women are known to have a higher emotional intelligence, they are not being featured in the police field. Studies have had significant findings where women have exceptionally outranked men in emotional intelligence. This includes being able to regulate their feelings, having empathy for others, and being able to balance interpersonal relationships (Meshkat & Nejati, 2017). With relation to past research there was a significant

finding where criminal justice majors have less empathy compared to other majors (Courtright, Mackey, and Packard, 2005). With the general understanding that criminal justice majors may lack empathy, men having lower emotional intelligence, and the police force is a male dominated career, there is a recognizable relationship with men choosing the career path of becoming a police officer.

Other Interesting Findings

Other interesting findings were noticed between the relationship with ethnicity and choosing their greatest influence for becoming a criminal justice major. There was a noticeable difference where all ethnicities, except for Black participants chose “general interest” for their greatest influence. “Generational” was the highest chosen answer for Black participants. I also noticed every ethnicity chose “generational” and “personal experiences” for their greatest influence. I also looked at ethnicity and career interest and found the top highest career interest amongst each ethnicity. For White participants, it was “police officer”, for Black participants there was three-way tie between “lawyer/judge,” “detective/agent/investigator,” and “forensic psychologist,” for Latinx participants the top choice was “detective/agent/investigator,” for Asian participants the top choice was “detective/agent/investigator,” for Other/Multiple ethnicities, the top choice was “police officer” and lastly, the participants who preferred not to say their ethnicity, it was also a three way tie between, “lawyer/judge,” “detective/agent/investigator,” and “professor/teacher.”

Though the results of this survey focus on criminal justice majors, it can also demonstrate what important factors students take into consideration when generally choosing a major. For example, their gender alone can determine why they chose a certain major. The results also establish that personal experiences make a difference in why some students choose their major.

When students are choosing their major and career path, they can remind themselves about these factors and hopefully better understand which major would be best for them.

Conclusion

While these findings are interesting and shed light on why students chose to become criminal justice majors, there are some limitations that must be acknowledged. A limitation was the low response rate of 14% of the criminal justice students that participated in the survey. With a low response rate, it was not a full representation of CSUF criminal justice students. There is no evidence to show that it had reached every student associated with the criminal justice department, but through the mass email sent out it is safe to say that it had reached a majority. With a low response rate, it is encouraged to conduct future research with a more student participation. There should also be a longer duration to take the survey. Unfortunately, I only allowed three weeks for students to complete the survey, but if there was a longer time period with multiple reminders there could be a higher response rate. There could also be incentives to take the survey, such as a chance in a raffle to win a gift card.

Another issue is generalizability. This study was conducted with a small number of students at one university. In order to improve generalizability, I suggest conducting the study at more colleges or universities.

This research project has been a struggle and a tremendous accomplishment in my undergraduate career. Creating a plan for this project, finding the necessary research involved for my study, and going through the IRB process was essential to this project, but also time consuming. At first, I planned to use student and professor participants, but due to time constraints I was not able to include the interviews of the professors. The students identified the motivations they chose their majors, but the professors would have provided how if their

motivations have changed and if they are satisfied with their criminal field focus choice. I also wanted to compare their motivation to join the criminal justice field to their professional focus.

Although I did not use professor participants, I still used student's participation. When using any human subjects, I need to receive the IRB approval. This assured the protection of all human participants' ethical rights. I now understand the lengthy process of securing IRB approval that must be taken well before the data collection is set to begin. With the results found in this study, I hope future students who are choosing their major think about these important factors and can apply it to themselves in order to find their major that is best for them.

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